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A framework for regional high-level technical screening of promising CCUS value chains

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Author: Ane Elisabet Lothe (SINTEF), Isaline Gravaud (BRGM), Eirik Falck da Silva (SINTEF), Ragnhild Skagestad (SINTEF), Alla Shogenova (TalTech), Kazbulat Shogenov (TalTech), Leandro Sousa (Romboll), Adam Wójcickif, Çağlar Sınayuç (METU-PAL), Betül Yıldırım (METU-PAL), Sevtaç Bülbül (METU-PAL), Anastasios Perimenisi (CO₂ Value Europe), Laurianne Bouvier (Axelera)

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WP Leader or co-leader	Ane Elisabet Lothe	 <small>Ane Elisabet Lothe (May 13, 2025 13:04 GMT+2)</small>	13/05/25
Project Coordinator	Eirik Falck da Silva		13/05/25

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Executive summary

There is a need to accelerate the deployment of Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) throughout Europe. As a part of this, the CCUS ZEN project has looked at how to carry out high-level technical screening of promising value chains with technical mapping of emission sources, utilization options, transport infrastructure and storage sites. In this report challenges in the high-level technical CCUS value chain workflow is discussed.

First, a screening of the emission sources in each geographical region led to the identification of promising sites for CO₂ capture. The focus is on identifying clusters of emitters, where CO₂ could be captured from different industrial plants and gathered at a hub before transport to the storage site. The emitters can also be identified as promising depending on their amount of emission, location, type of industry, etc. For each emission source, information about the facility was collected, along with information about the facility's emissions. The screening of potential storage sites in the geographical region was carried out based on public and available data from projects. For each mapped storage site, information was gathered about the type of reservoir (deep saline aquifer or depleted hydrocarbon field), the onshore or offshore location, the capacity of the reservoir and the Storage Readiness Level indicating the maturity of the capacity evaluation. For the infrastructure screening, we looked at existing infrastructure relevant for CO₂-transport with emphasis on pipelines, existing natural gas corridors, waterways and ports. If transport using pipelines or waterways were not an option, also railways and road (lorries) were evaluated.

Thereafter, one or more chains were suggested, linking one or more emission clusters to one or more storage sites. The total emission volumes of the clusters and the storage capacities were considered. It was recognised that actual volumes should be treated with caution. On the one hand, the maturity level of the storage sites is often low, resulting in potential smaller capacities when the resource is further assessed. Also, crucial data can be missing or confidential, which makes detailed studies and dynamic reservoir modelling challenging. On the other hand, the total volumes of the clusters' emission do not necessarily represent the amount of captured CO₂, but rather a maximum, as not 100% of the emissions would necessarily be captured. The potential for carbon utilisation was assessed by identifying existing CO₂ use projects and looking at the potential availability of renewable energy and biogenic CO₂.

Finally, lessons learned from CCUS value chains around the world were discussed and some recommendations are made. The main recommendations are:

- Datasets for CO₂ storage should be made more accessible
- There should be open dialogue between stakeholders across the value chain
- There should be open dialogue with societal stakeholders

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A framework for regional high-level technical screening of promising CCUS value chains

1 Introduction

This report is Deliverable 1.3 of the CCUS ZEN - Zero Emission Network to facilitate CCUS uptake in industrial clusters project, an EU funded network project running from autumn 2023 till spring 2025. The overall aim with the project is to accelerate the deployment of Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) throughout Europe, and to explore the potential for CCUS value chain deployed in two regions: the Baltic Sea region and the Mediterranean Sea region. The two regions, have until now low maturity level of CCUS compared to the development in the North Sea region. In the project, different forms of studies have been carried out, starting from high-level regional screening both of technical mapping and non-technical mapping, till selection of promising CCUS value chain, and finally study of full deployment cases in the two regions (see Figure 1-1).

As part of the project, first a high-level technical mapping was carried out for the two regions as presented in D1.1 (Ringstad et al. 2023). This report covers technical mapping of emission sources, storage sites, transport infrastructure, utilization options and renewables. Thereafter, CCUS value chains both in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions were mapped, and in the end the eight most promising sites were selected as shown in report D1.2 (Gravaud et al. 2024). The overall screening workflow was tested in the two geographical regions and led to the definition of at least 15 CCUS value chains, several with different transport solution included, using ships or pipelines or a combination (Gravaud et al. 2024). Based on the previous work carried out in the CCUS ZEN project, this report will sum up the technical requirements for a high-level screening for CCUS value chain, as shown in the green box in Figure 1-1. Lessons learned from operating and developing CCUS cluster projects worldwide will be integrated in the framework. The main challenges and obstacles in the CCUS ZEN high-level screening will be discussed and recommendations for further work will be given.

Figure 1-1 Overview of the work tasks in the CCUS ZEN project, with the technical mapping marked in green.

2 High-level CCUS technical value chain screening

In the regional screening carried out in the CCUS ZEN project, technical and non-technical mappings were carried out. The technical mapping focused on emission sources, storage sites, transport infrastructure, utilization options and renewables. The non-technical mapping included stakeholders needs, regulations, climate policies and funding opportunities (Figure 1-1). These aspects should be considered, when CCUS value chain are to be developed further after the initial technical high-level screening.

Several studies have been carried out focus on high-level CCUS value chain screening with focus on scenario development (Jakobsen & Brunsvold 2011), infrastructure (Kjärstad & Johnsson 2009), or storage sites (e.g. Anthonsen et al. 2014).

The high-level CCUS technical value chain can be subdivided into four main parts covering mapping of CO₂ emitters, infrastructure screening, storage sites screening and utilization as a final piece in the puzzle (see Figure 2-1). For each part of the value chain, several key input parameters are listed without ranking the importance, costs, or effort to get enough data to draw solid conclusion. This will be addressed further in this report.

As part of the high-level CCUS technical screening, an open geographical information system (QGIS¹) has been used for mapping the emitters and storage sites from previous reports, and to illustrate emission clusters and possible transport routes, both existing and future infrastructures.

Figure 2-1 Principal sketch presenting the main components to consider in the high-level technical CCUS value chain screening.

¹ [Spatial without Compromise - QGIS Web Site](#)

3 Industry clusters

For the industry clusters we subdivide between the mapping of emitters and utilization, mainly mapping ongoing projects and technology options.

3.1 Mapping of emitters

First, a screening of the emission sources in each geographical region leads to the identification of promising sites for CO₂ capture. The focus was on identifying clusters of emitters, where CO₂ could be captured from different industrial sites and gathered at a hub before common transport to storage. Yet, standalone emitters can also be identified as promising for CCUS value chains, depending on their amount of emission, location, type of industry, etc. For each emission source, information about the facility was collected (facility name, company, location, coordinates, and industrial sector), along with information about the facility's emissions (annual amount of CO₂ emitted, emissions trend, share of biomass, and waste-to-energy).

In the CCUS ZEN project, the reported CO₂ emissions collected in Ringstad et al. (2023) are in general from 2021, except for some facilities where only older data are available. Clusters are defined, with the total amount of emissions, the number of facilities in the cluster, and the share of each industrial sector in the total emissions. Data from CaptureMap provided by the company Endrava² are used for mapping CO₂ emissions sources in the Baltic Sea region (Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland) and the Mediterranean Sea region (France, Spain, Italy, Greece, Türkiye). The emission data were quality-checked, and amended where necessary, by the CCUS ZEN partners in Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and France. Since Türkiye was not covered in the CaptureMap database, this mapping was carried out by the Türkiye partner. Overview of CO₂ emission sources is shown in Figure 3-1.

3.1.1 Challenges in mapping of emitters

When mapping emitters, several questions need to be addressed:

1) Mapping of all emitters, are all mapped?

The CO₂ emission database in CaptureMap, provided by ENDRAVA is mainly sourced from

- the EU Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS) and
- the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)

The EU-ETS data mainly includes the fossil-based CO₂ emissions, whereas the E-PRTR includes both fossil-based and biogenic CO₂ emissions. The E-PRTR dataset only includes the facilities with CO₂ emissions above 100 ktpa, while the EU ETS dataset also includes the facilities with smaller emission volumes (<100 ktpa). Since CaptureMap use the E-PRTR system as their basis for facilities in European countries, many facilities with CO₂ emissions

² [CaptureMap - Find the best decarbonisation opportunities](#)

less than 100 ktpa are not included in CaptureMap database. There has also been some inconsistency between the EU ETS and E-PRTR databases for several facilities. Regarding the quality check of CaptureMap data, only a few discrepancies were identified, mainly from the recent updates from facilities in Estonia, Lithuania and Poland. On the other hand, the data from Germany, Spain, Italy and Greece could not be quality checked; thus, has directly been implemented in further analysis.

Since data from Türkiye was not available in the CO₂ emission database of CaptureMap, mapping of emission data in Türkiye were carried out as part of the CCUS ZEN project, see more details in Ringstad et al. (2023). Due to the unavailability of annual, sector-based CO₂ emission data, the mapping of CO₂ emission sources in Türkiye has been restricted to emissions from the leading sectors in terms of CO₂ emissions, namely the refineries and petrochemical industry, power plants, iron and steel industry, and cement industry.

Figure 3-1 Overview of CO₂ emission sources and storage sites in the two study areas; the Baltic region marked with dark green and Mediterranean area with very light green. Light green areas, shows area protected by the Natura 2000.

2) What should be the threshold for mapping of emitter sources in CO₂ tonnes/year?

In our approach, all the main emitters are mapped, and the minimum amount, in the more detailed analysis is set to 100 ktpa.

3) How to handle and report biogenic emissions?

In CCUS ZEN project it was decided to map biogenic CO₂ emissions and distinguish them from fossil CO₂ emissions where it was possible. At the present time the EU plants producing biogenic CO₂ are not obliged to pay taxes and to report their CO₂ emissions to EU ETS. However, if the plant is applied co-combustion process, using fossil fuel together with biofuel, they have to report their total CO₂ emissions to EU ETS, but pay taxes only for fossil fuel CO₂ emissions. Therefore, at national level, co-combustion plants have to report both their biogenic CO₂ and fossil CO₂ – separately and together, and such regulations are already introduced in some of the EU countries. For example, France reports for biogenic, non-biogenic, and total CO₂ emissions in the IREP database³, while Estonian plants are reporting annually their bio and fossil CO₂ emissions in national reports⁴. Maps and data of the main industrial CO₂ emitters in Europe are accessible from the European Industrial Emissions Portal⁵. However, in this portal some plants producing bio-CO₂ are already reporting their emissions, not specifying which part are fossil and which are bio-emissions, while other plants do not yet report their CO₂ emissions.

Some countries have not yet required reporting of biogenic CO₂ emissions (for example Latvia), because they are not yet a subject for CO₂ taxes or other financial incentives to capture biogenetic CO₂. Also, not all EU countries have introduced national CO₂ taxes⁶. Another question is if national carbon taxes or financial incentives to capture CO₂ will be extended to biogenic CO₂ emissions. At the present time CO₂ taxation in EU ETS and national CO₂ taxations are different regulations and the last ones are not uniform in different EU countries. The EU is working on a regulatory framework for the certification of carbon removals, the application of which (market and regulatory demand) remains uncertain (European Commission, 2024). When the new regulations will be introduced, all EU plants will be obliged to report their biogenic CO₂ both at national and EU levels. In Poland in yearly reports of Institute of Environmental Protection (the most recent by Waszczytko-Miłkowska, 2024) inventories on waste treatment in industrial installations are published. These data include waste incineration in waste to energy plants and co-combustion in cement and power plants (amount of waste, not CO₂ emissions, but emissions can be easily calculated when we have amount of waste incinerated, e.g. assuming 1 t waste = 1 t CO₂). Not all these data were included in ENDRAVA database, particularly in case of cement plants.

Waste to energy plants represent a relatively new business in Europe. CO₂ capture technology is already available for these new plants. The Hafslund Oslo Celsio waste to energy plant in Norway is carrying out a FEED study for CCS. Waste to energy plants

³ <https://www.georisques.gouv.fr/risques/registre-des-emissions-polluantes/etablissement/donnees/>

⁴ KOTKAS - AVE v2.12.3 (envir.ee)

⁵ <https://www.industry.eea.europa.eu/explore/explore-datamap/>

⁶ Carbon Pricing Dashboard | Up-to-date overview of carbon pricing initiatives (worldbank.org)

normally produce a high share of biogenic CO₂ emissions. When capturing and storing bio-CO₂, negative CO₂ emissions can be generated, that can be certified, and these certificates could be sold to any enterprise in the world.

Ørsted Bioenergy & Thermal Power A/S in Denmark will capture 430,000 tonnes of biogenic CO₂ from the Asnæs and Avedøre combined heat and power stations. Captured CO₂ will be shipped to the Northern Lights storage reservoir in the Norwegian part of the North Sea. This stored biogenic CO₂ will be certified. Microsoft has agreed to purchase 2.67 million tonnes of certified CO₂ removal over 11 years. This will help Microsoft to meet their climate commitments. In Poland about 1.1 Mt of municipal waste is incinerated in 8 WtE plants and about 0.96 Mt waste is co-combusted in cement plants (Waszczyłko-Miłkowska, 2024), including Holcim cement plant Kujawy where capture installation is to be constructed by 2027⁷.

4) *What kind of emission sources should be prioritized for capture?*

The emission sources are subdivided depending on type of industry, varying from refineries, chemicals, power, hydrogen, energy from waste, cement, paper and pulp, iron and steel and others. There is some complexity in deciding which industrial sites should be prioritised for CCS. For some industries CCS is the obvious option to reduce emissions, while in other cases CCS may be one of several options (some form of electrification often being another). The level of CO₂ emissions in the future and longevity of an industrial plant can also be a factor in considering the deployment of CCS. Information on this is however difficult to obtain. Information can be commercially sensitive and there may also political considerations that are hard for us to assess. For this reason, in this high-level screening, only the current emission levels from different industries are considered.

5) *How to choose the emitters hubs?*

When choosing the emitters hub, several factors were evaluated, as shown in Figure 2-1. The type of industry, the number of emission sources and not at least location are very important factors. If there are several large industry clusters, that can share common infrastructure, like pipelines and/or buffer storage and/or ship transport, this can be very central for building out an emission hub. Also, the possibility to share a storage site would be beneficial for the emitters and for the one owning the storage site. In the high-level screening, the emitters are mapped, but not its details. Example of mapped CCUS value chain is shown for Türkiye-Greece (Figure 3-2), with emission clusters in Türkiye, possible pipeline on the mainland, and ship transport to offshore storage south of Greece. In Denmark, with more data from possible storage sites (e.g. Anthonsen et al. 2014, Hjelm et al. 2020), several storage sites have been selected in the CCUS workflow, and thereby also several industry clusters have been included in the high-level screening (Gravaud et al. 2024).

⁷ Go4ECOPlanet project

Figure 3-2 Example of how two CO₂ emitters hubs; the Soma Cluster and İzmir Aliğa Cluster can combine CO₂ transport possible by pipelines, and stored in a site offshore Greece (Prinos area). From Gravaud et al. (2024).

3.2 Utilisation

Carbon Capture and Utilisation represents an array of diverse technologies that can capture carbon from industrial installations or directly from the air and use it as feedstock to produce marketable products like fuels, chemicals and materials. CO₂ use options both conversional and non-conversional (direct use) are summed up in Figure 3-3 below.

A full technological scouting was performed for the CO₂ conversion pathways available at the European level. The objective of the technological scouting was to identify the emerging and disruptive technologies that could make CCU industrially viable at European level, particularly in Mediterranean and Baltic area.

One focuses on the main following pathways, mineralisation, renewable fuels and chemical products, highlighting the following details:

- Technology name and type
- Electricity needs
- Main existing technological approach
- Estimated conversion factor
- Molecules produced and reactions
- Estimated costs
- Technology Readiness Level
- Specific conditions for implementation
- Main key sectors for the use of the technology
- Technology advantages and drawbacks
- Involved stakeholders in this technology.

Focusing on Mediterranean area, different clusters were identified for CO₂ emissions. For example, in Tarragona cluster, mapping of emitters revealed that more than 80% of CO₂ emissions are coming from refineries and production of chemicals. In Barcelona cluster, more than 80% of CO₂ emissions are coming from power and cement /lime industries. In Fos-Marseille cluster, more than 40% of CO₂ emissions are coming from iron & steel industries, then equally from power, refineries and chemical industries. The port of Marseille-Fos is the largest port in France in terms of goods and the 3rd one in Mediterranean area.

Decarbonation of the maritime sector is a key challenge and production of e-fuels for the maritime sector might be an option. A e-fuel will obviously be combusted shortly after being produced and the CO₂ will then be emitted. The environmental benefit of using such an e-fuel will depend on the sourcing of energy and the CO₂.

Figure 3-3 CO₂ use options through conversion into other products or direct use. Figure from IEA 2019.

3.2.1 Challenge in utilization

Recently, utilisation of captured carbon has been receiving more attention in the discussion of technological solutions that will help EU reach its climate neutrality goal for 2050. Nevertheless, there are still challenges that need to be overcome to see CCU deploy at industrial scale all over Europe.

An inherent feature of many forms of CCU is that the chemical conversions require energy. For this to make sense from an environmental perspective that energy will need to be renewable. Many forms of CCU are therefore contingent on the availability of renewable energy.

Despite the acknowledgment in recent policy instruments (e.g. Net Zero Industry Act, Industrial Carbon Management Policy) a challenge observed in CCU is that, due to its diverse nature spanning across different sectors, many instruments are regulating its deployment with the risk of inconsistent elements appearing. While there are instruments promoting the use of CCU products in particular downstream sectors (e.g. ReFuel EU Aviation, Fuel EU Maritime) there are other instruments that come with limitations, for example on the accessibility to renewable electricity or the eligibility of the CO₂ to be reused based on its origin (see REDII Delegated acts) that might put at risk the exact same goals that have been agreed upon on the downstream. Additionally, one can observe that captured carbon as a circular and alternative carbon feedstock has not yet received the recognition it merits in policy, on the contrary it is being penalised against its virgin fossil counterpart; for example; the carbon embedded in a chemical molecule produced from fossil carbon is not being accounted for, but when the same chemical is produced from captured

carbon, the carbon embedded in it has been accounted for upstream as an emission. These few examples highlight elements of uncertainty in the legal framework that blocks investments in further deployment of such technologies.

The choice of the CCU route to follow is a task that requires a holistic approach as the one followed within CCUS ZEN. Elements to consider are the availability and the origin of the CO₂, the availability of renewable or low carbon electricity, the availability and existing use of industrial waste fractions (particularly for mineralisation), the potential for symbiotic relations among industries that share inputs and outputs, as well as the market for the final product. Some geographical settings and some industrial hubs might be more favourable than others to deploy a CCU solution.

In any case, the unprecedented policy making phase that we have experienced the last 2-3 years slowly gives its place to the implementation phase where the actual building of facilities is set to happen. Many CCU projects at industrial scale (see Deliverables 1.1 and 3.1) are expected to become operational by 2030 and the key to this upscaling effort will be the support of the policy framework and the financing of first movers from national and European instruments. Instruments like the Innovation Fund or the IPCEIs, together with strategic prioritisation at Member State level of CCU technologies that provide emission reductions under proven Life Cycle Assessment standards will be integral in the large-scale deployment and replication of CCU.

4 Transport infrastructure screening

The most important parameter to decide the transport mode is the volume of CO₂ to be transported, and the distance between source and storage. In addition, the available infrastructure already in place like pipeline gates, waterways, harbours, roads, railways may have impact on which transport mode is most viable.

4.1 Transport modes

The main transport modes are:

- Pipelines (onshore or offshore)
Existing pipelines could either be reused if they have the specification needed (temperature and pressure limitations, material etc) or the pipeline corridor can be used as a route for a new CO₂ pipeline. Depending on the pressure requirement in the reservoir, it may be suitable to use booster pumps.
- Ship and barges; varying pressure and temperatures will define different design of the vessels
- Railways
- Road transport by lorries
- Intermediate storage is needed where the transport mode is batchwise like for instance ship, railway and lorry transport

4.1.1 Criteria for choice of transport modes

The choice of transport modes is dependent on several factors; the main ones are listed below:

- **Source and type of CO₂ emissions:** The type of industry and CO₂ concentration can influence the choice of transport method.
- **Distance to storage site:** The length of the transport route can determine whether pipelines or ships are most appropriate.
- **Amount of CO₂ to be transported:** Large volumes may be more cost-effective to transport via pipelines.
- **Infrastructure costs:** Investment in new infrastructure such as pipelines or adaptation of ships can have a significant economic impact.
- **Geographical and logistical challenges:** Terrain, climate, and access to existing infrastructure can limit transport options.
- **Regulatory requirements:** Legislation and safety standards can influence the choice of transport method and route.
- **Environmental impact:** Minimizing the environmental footprint during transport is important for sustainable CCS solutions.
- **Future plans for source/ storage-** how is the future plans for the sources? Timeline for production/ changes in the emissions may affect the choice of transport model.

4.2 How did we do the infrastructure screening?

For the infrastructure screening, we were investigating if existing infrastructure are relevant for CO₂ transport with emphasis on pipelines, existing natural gas corridors, waterways and ports. If transport using pipelines or waterways were not an option, also railways and road (lorries) were evaluated. For transportation, the mapping tool developed in the CO₂LOS project was used to identify opportunities in ship transport or barges, while PCI Transparency Platform, combined with OpenStreetMap, was used for pipelines.

4.3 Challenges in choice of transport mode

The layout of infrastructure required for the transportation of CO₂ can be very complex and varies depending on the type of transportation selected. This impacts the equipment used for CO₂ conditioning and the necessity of intermediate storage. Figure 4-1 shows a representation of a potential CO₂ value chain and different components involved for different transportation methods. Often, several transportation modes can be used for the same value chain.

Different value drivers will condition the selection of transport modes for each particular case as defined in section 4.1.1. Nonetheless this selection must be followed with an analysis of the potential challenges which could require mitigations or a complete pivot of the concept. The main ones are developed below.

Pipelines: The usual low OPEX per tonne of CO₂ is often contrasted by a need for high initial investment in CAPEX. This includes the need to negotiate property access and right of way, which particularly for long pipelines can have a more unpredictable price and set-up time. Pipelines are often buried for protection which reduces the risk of damage but allows for less

flexibility and long-term planning. Additionally, rupture of high-pressure CO₂ (dense or supercritical phases) can lead to fracture propagation during phase change, becoming a major hazard. These challenges are mitigated by increasing the pipeline material resistance.

Lorries: Although a flexible solution suitable for short-distance transportation, the utilisation of lorries often means a high OPEX per tonne of CO₂, despite of a lower CAPEX. They also require manual handling for loading, unloading and transport. Lorries lead to increased traffic and are more exposed to road conditions and traffic accidents. Each lorry has a limited capacity. If the lorries do not use green or low carbon energy sources, there will be emissions related to the transport operation.

Railway: Railway transportation can be suitable for longer distance onshore transportation. CAPEX is highly influenced by the need to convert rail infrastructure. Intermediate storage may also be quite sizeable. Rail infrastructure has limited access and is often supplemented by an additional transport mode.

Ships

In contrast to lorries or railway transportation, ships require a large volume capacity to be economical viable. Therefore, it also requires large intermediate storage hubs at the loading and unloading locations. Its accessibility is limited to offshore/rivers and to the availability of ports. Ships are also limited by the ports access conditions, which may limit the maximum ship size. Alternatively, a (rather high) investment can be made to improve the port accessibility.

Additional considerations must be considered when selecting the transport mode which include health, safety, integrity and CO₂ phase behaviour aspects. Impurities in the CO₂ stream play an important role, potentially causing corrosion, embrittlement or changing the CO₂ phase to more unpredictable behaviour. Safety concerns also include asphyxiation or toxicity due to unexpected release, low temperature hazard and rapid expansion due to sudden decompression and subsequent lack of visibility due to water vapour cloud formation. Onshore transportation and particularly storage tanks (due to high volume enclosed in potentially manned sites) must be analysed thoroughly from a safety perspective due to the potential concerns affecting 1st and 3rd parties in case of failure.

Figure 4-1: Representation of a CO₂ value chain process considering mixed, i.e., ship and pipeline, transportation.

5 Storage sites

There are two main categories for underground carbon dioxide storage; using saline aquifers or depleted reservoirs that have been used for previous oil and gas production. Other geological storage options, like mineral carbonisation was not considered, since such sites have not been mapped in detailed in the previous projects. The main reason that was mentioned in D.1.1 is the absence of the large basalt formations with needed geological properties (depth and porosity) in the studied regions.

In the high-level screening of potential storage sites in the geographical sectors in the CCUS ZEN project, the screening was carried out and based on public and available data from European projects such as GESTCO, GeoCapacity, CO2Stop, NORDICCS, Strategy CCUS, PilotSTRATEGY, and national projects. For each mapped storage site, information was gathered about the type of reservoir (deep saline aquifer or depleted hydrocarbon field), the onshore or offshore location, the capacity of the reservoir (mean value), and the storage readiness level (SRL) indicating the maturity of the capacity evaluation based on Akhurst et al. (2019).

5.1 Storage capacity estimation

The amount of CO₂ to be stored underground, is very much dependent on the media for the storage and the injectivity. The subsurface storage aquifers or permeable geological formation can be defined as a regional aquifer, a storage assessment unit (SAU), and has an upper limit defined by where the CO₂ will be in supercritical phase (approximately below 800 m depth, depending on pressures and temperature variations), Figure 5-1. The lower limit is defined by the porosity and permeability to the reservoir units and will be defined on what is seen as an acceptable injection rate. In the CCUS ZEN project, the classification of storage structures is built on methodology outlined in Gammer et al. (2011).

There exist several methods to calculate storage capacity. The storage capacity can in general terms be described as the pore volume of the aquifer in the SAU region multiplied with the storage efficiency factor (fraction of pore space where CO₂ “can” be injected). In the CCUS ZEN project, the Vangkilde-Pedersen et al. (2009) capacity formulas have been used (Ringstad et al. 2023).

Figure 5-1 Schematic cross section with storage assessment unit shown. From Brennan et al. (2010).

5.2 Challenge in storage screening

When mapping storage sites, several challenges occur:

1) Lack of data or lack of data access

In the CCUS ZEN project we had project partners from the two geographical regions in the project. Even with many research institutes and key industry actors involved, it was challenging to get access to datasets to make reliable estimates for storage potential. The underlying datasets needed such as interpreted 2D seismic or 3D seismic, data from existing wells, geological models and/or reservoir models are seldom publicly available. For the North Sea, several data sets from the Sleipner area and the Smeaheia area have been shared by the CO₂ DataShare⁸ web portal. CO₂ DataShare aims to share high-quality datasets from pilot, demonstration and industry-scale projects to enable research on CO₂ storage. However, in other parts of Europe, data access is more challenging.

Scarce data cover is a major challenge in many regions, and in CCUS ZEN, the mapping of storage sites was heavily relying on previous research projects. As the screening of potential storage sites was based on public and available data, it resulted in varying mapping coverage. For instance, for Italy, only some storage sites were included in the CCUS ZEN project database and high-level mapping, even we were aware that several other storage

⁸ <https://co2datashare.org/>

sites previously have been evaluated for CO₂ and/or hydrogen storage, e.g. Barison et al. (2023).

2) Challenge in finding large enough storage units

Another challenge related to storage sites mapping is the capacity of these potential storage sites. Indeed, databases present a large number of sites with too little storage capacity for an operational CCS project to take place. For example, in Southern France, existing capacity data are on the order of few tens of Mt, even smaller, per site. It is then challenging to find sufficient storage capacity for the identified emission clusters and build large-scale value chains. This is also a reason why transnational scenarios were developed. Finland is lacking any storage potential, since they have only bedrocks, and therefore the selected value chain suggested in CCUS ZEN is pipeline or ship transport from Helsinki, Finland to Rødby, storage site in Denmark (Gravaud et al. 2024). Sweden has sedimentary deposits in the Baltic Sea, like the Cambrian Faludden Formation, but with low storage potential e.g. dipping aquifer, with small natural closures e.g. Lothe et al. (2016). However, the structures continue southwards at Polish side, and may serve as a potential storage structures.

3) Competing interests between CCS and geothermal and/or HC production

Mapped in a number of European countries, extensive and relatively deep onshore regional Mesozoic aquifers including local traps (e.g. anticlinal structures) can be used both for CCS and geothermal purposes. For example, regional Lower Jurassic aquifer covering large part of Poland is deemed as one of primary geothermal reservoirs of the country and is utilized in a number of district heating (and other) geothermal installations and many such geothermal projects are being completed or planned now. However, if CCS projects would use local traps/structures located outside population centres where district heating could be switched to geothermal, then such competition could be mitigated.

Both in the northern and southern North Sea are competing interests with the oil and gas industry, not so much on the areas, as CO₂ licences are awarded by the governments, but we foresee on the pore pressures. If CO₂ storage will lead to higher pressures in some reservoirs or aquifer, these may have an impact on neighbouring CO₂ storage sites and/or oil and gas production. However, these challenges have not been evaluated in the CO₂ storage screening but should be considered in future dynamic simulations.

Regarding Türkiye' s case, the CO₂ injection into the underground formations has been mainly being performed as part of the enhanced oil recovery (EOR) process in a heavy oil reservoir (Batı Raman field), which is in the southeastern region of country. Besides, the injected CO₂ has not been captured from a facility, but rather been transported from a nearby, naturally CO₂ producing field (Dodan field) in the same region. Accordingly, even though there is enough data on the characteristics of still producing hydrocarbon reservoirs (such as porosity, permeability, fluid saturations, depth, thickness, trap mechanisms etc.), there is still no practical experience on the CO₂ injectivity in depleted oil and gas reservoirs. Furthermore, even though both the hydrocarbon and the natural CO₂ reservoirs might serve as the CO₂ storage fields once they are depleted in the near future, the storage capacity of such fields is estimated to be limited mainly to local emissions in the same region. On the other hand, despite the fact that the larger-capacity saline aquifers prevail over the country, there is currently no/limited database available on the characteristics and so on the technical and economic feasibility of CO₂ storage in these fields.

4) Challenge in comparing storage capacities with little input data available

The CO₂ storage capacity provides important information about a CO₂ storage site. However, the estimation alone does not consider all factors that influence feasibility of a prospective site for an operational CO₂ storage project. To communicate the maturity of a CO₂ storage site and what remains for it to become operative, Akhurst et al. (2021) introduced the CO₂ Storage Readiness Level (SRL) concept. CCUS ZEN has applied the SRL scheme when evaluating the maturity of potential CO₂ storage sites. It was concluded that the majority of the identified storage sites has low SRL, particularly in the Mediterranean region. Sites with higher maturity present lower capacities.

Some countries have enough storage sites, but low SRL. This is the situation offshore in the Mediterranean, with few high 2D and 3D quality data sets open available for researcher and academia. Either because of old data, lacking data, or lacking open datasets for instance for saline aquifers. In areas with no hydrocarbon prospective, no or very few wells are drilled.

5) Effect of natural and/or induced seismicity and considerations of Natura2000

In the CCUS ZEN project we faced uncertainties due the location of the potential storage within – or partially covering – the perimeter of protected areas, such as Natura2000, or even Natural Park in Southern France. Even if CO₂ storage in such area is not prohibited, this status will require more detailed environmental impact studies in the administrative processes. This may influence the process of authorisation and licensing.

From seismic risk maps, we see that Italy, Greece and Turkey have higher risks for natural earthquakes than other part of Europe, due to plate movements (Figure 5-2). Thus, there are laterally variations, and possible storage sites should carry out detailed analysis. We know from Japan, that offshore underground CO₂ storage in seismic tectonic active area has been tested, with extensive monitoring systems (Sawada et al. 2018, Tanase et al. 2021). 3 ktonnes of CO₂ was stored from April 2016 to November 2019, at the Tomakomai CCS Demonstration Project. A total of thirteen events om moment magnitude ranging from -0.04 to 0.5 Mw were detected in the basement, but no seismicity occurred at and around the depth of the reservoir. The 2018 Hokkaido Eastern Iburu Earthquake of magnitude 6.6 Mw did not affect the stored CO₂, and no data showed any connection between the earthquake and the CO₂ storage (Tanase et al. 2021).

In some regions, the challenges can be opposite, that the community is afraid of induced seismicity due to CO₂ storage. The choice of the storage will have to take into account the risk of inducing seismicity. As required by the EU CCS Directive, a CO₂ storage operator has to demonstrate that the planned operations present no significant risks for health and environment, including risk of generating “felt” seismicity when injecting CO₂. Careful study of the storage complex should be performed, especially the identification and assessment of existing faults and fractures that could be reactivated by the injection operations.

Figure 5-2 European seismic risk map with high risk mapped for eastern part of Mediterranean countries. Colour scale shows seismic risks. From [EFHR Risk Maps - European Seismic Risk Index Viewer \(eucentre.it\)](https://www.eucentre.it/EFHR/RiskMaps/).

6 Lessons learned from CCUS cluster projects world-wide

If one evaluates CCUS cluster projects worldwide, we see both technical challenges connected to emitters, transport, and storage, but many of the challenges are non-technical such as lack of funding (examples of that are the Road project in the Netherlands that was stopped and Peterhead in the UK, that was stopped, see overview in Gough & Mander 2022), or projects in Poland and Italy that had industry support, but not governmental support.

In Norway, the underground storage in the Utsira Formation, at Sleipner Field, offshore Norway started already in 1996 (e.g., Zweigel et al. 2004, Furre et al. 2024). One of the reasons for execution of this project was that the CO₂ sequestration was carried out as a part of the natural gas production. The CO₂ was injected in fluid phase in a shallow aquifer around 800 m beneath the surface and stored. An incentive for this project was a tax on CO₂ emissions that had been instituted by the Norwegian government in 1991. CO₂ capture (in this context referred to as natural gas sweetening) was already a part of the natural gas production, so in this case there was only investments required for CO₂ storage.

Lack of business cases and incentives

CCS can be thought of as a waste disposal. Instead of polluting the atmosphere with CO₂ one captures it and stores it. In the absence of penalties or incentives polluting will be cheaper than waste management. The main reason for CCS not having been deployed at a substantial scale until now is that the financial incentives to do so have not been sufficient. Most past project initiatives relied heavily on government subsidies. Many project cancellations were related to lack of sufficient funding or failure of the project to come to

agreement on terms with governments. Examples of this are the ROAD project, Peterhead and Full-scale Mongstad (in Norway).

Today the gap between cost of emitting CO₂ and cost of CCS is smaller, but government intervention is still expected to play a significant role in realizing early CCS value chains. There are still questions to be resolved on the best way to incentivize the realisation of CCS value chains.

Challenge with injectivity

At the Snøhvit field located in the Barents Sea, 150 km north of the mainland of Norway, 1.6 Mt CO₂ was injected in the Early Jurassic Tubåen Formation (sandstone unit) over three years (April 2008 to April 2011) (Hansen et al. 2013). During the injection, the operator experienced reduced injectivity that led to a pressure buildup in the Tubåen Fm. They then, had to carry out a well intervention, and use the shallower Early to Middle Jurassic Stø Formation sandstones for further CO₂ injection and storage. Salt precipitation was a possible source for reducing of the near well injectivity (see also Hansen et al. 2013, Grude et al. 2014 for more details).

Challenge with social acceptance

In general, it seems fair to say that the public awareness of CCS tends to be low. For some projects there does not appear to have been any major issues related to public acceptance. There have however been some cases in the past of serious acceptance issues, in particular relating to CO₂ storage. A notable example being the Barendrecht pilot-project in the Netherlands. It has observed that there were probably failures in stakeholder management in this project (Feenstra et al. 2010).

There seems to be no reason to expect major general issues with social acceptance for CCS project. The fact that this is new industry, and that the public awareness is low may suggest that the risk of mismanagement of stakeholders is still substantial.

Use of CO₂ for increased oil recovery, examples from Canada, US and Brazil

Injecting CO₂ into oil reservoirs to enhance oil recovery has been practiced on a commercial scale for nearly 50 years, with the first successful pilot tests conducted in the early 1960s in the state of Texas (Holm, 1987). The first operating CCUS cluster projects in the world are CO₂-EOR and storage projects in USA and Canada. The Alberta Carbon Trunk System is situated in Alberta, Canada. They capture CO₂ from emitters in the Alberta Industry Heartland and transport the CO₂, by pipeline to central and southern Alberta and stored in depleted oil reservoirs. The CO₂ pipeline with annual capacity of 14.6 Mt CO₂ is open access to all CO₂ producers in Alberta's Industrial Heartland and central Alberta.

Petrobras injected 10.6 million tons of CO₂ in 2022. It is around 25% of the total amount of CO₂ injected by the industry as a whole year, as stated by the Global CCS Institute. Currently, all 21 floating production and offloading operated by Petrobras that are working in the pre-salt of the Santos Basin apply capture technology for CO₂-EOR. Injecting the CO₂ into the reservoir increases oil production efficiency and reduces the overall GHG

emissions⁹. Using its unique experience in CO₂-EOR, Petrobras is now planning how to implement a CCS hub in Brazil, in partnership with other companies. The project will create an infrastructure for the CO₂ capture from industrial facilities, transport and storage in a reservoir below the seabed. The final goal is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions generated not only by Petrobras' operations, but also by other industries in the country, including cement manufacture, steelworks and others⁹.

7 Developing CCUS value chains in Europe

A full overview of developing CCUS value chains worldwide is listed by Wang (2024). Here, we give a brief overview of some key CCUS value chains in Europe.

Northern Lights is a joint venture between Shell, TotalEnergies and Equinor, and is developing a full-scale CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure that can receive CO₂ from emitters across Europe (Equinor report 2021). The storage site is situated at the Horda Platform, approximately 110 km west of Bergen, Norway. They plan to inject CO₂ into saline aquifers, the shallow-marine deposited sandstones of Lower Jurassic Dunlin Group and the Upper Triassic to Lower Jurassic Staffjord Group. The caprock is the marine claystone deposits in the Drake Formation (Meneguolo et al. 2024, Thompson et al. 2022). Northern Lights plans to develop the storage in two phases: Phase I with initial injectivity of 1.5 Mtpa that will start injecting in 2025, and thereafter it will be increased to 5 Mtpa per year in phase II¹⁰.

The Northern Endurance Partnership (NEP) in the UK is a transport and storage company that will deliver the onshore and offshore infrastructure needed to capture carbon of emitters across Teesside and Humber and transport the CO₂ for storage in the Endurance store¹¹. The Net Zero Teesside is based in Teesside in the northeastern part of England (Figure 7-1). It aims to decarbonize a cluster of carbon-intensive businesses by as early as 2030. Working in partnership with local industry and with committed the project plans to capture up to 10 Mt of CO₂ emissions¹².

The Humber is the most carbon intensive industrial cluster in UK, emitting 12.4 Mt CO₂ a year. Zero Carbon Humber (ZCH) project plans to produce hydrogen, capture CO₂ from the Drax Power Plant and industry and store it in the saline aquifer under the southern North Sea. In 2021 it was reported by UK consortium that UK Teesside cluster project and ZCH project will cooperate with CO₂ storage to the Endurance storage site under the North Sea. The Endurance structure is a four-way dip-closure within the 200 m thick Middle Jurassic Bunter Sandstone Formation reservoir in the Southern North Sea. The Bunter sandstones have in average 24% porosity, 450 mD permeability, and storage capacity of about 500 Mt. Endurance saline aquifer located at the depth of 1.1km and was drilled by 4 wells (Pale Blue Dot Energy, Axis Well Technology report 2016). Equinor-led Hydrogen to Humber (H2H) Saltend is ZCH 's anchor project. It will establish the world's largest hydrogen production

⁹ <https://agencia.petrobras.com.br/>

¹⁰ [Northern Lights EU funding approved - Northern Lights \(norlights.com\)](#)

¹¹ [NSTA awards Endurance first ever UK carbon storage permit](#)

¹² <https://www.netzeroteesside.co.uk/>

plant with carbon capture at Saltend Chemicals Park. All captured CO₂ will be compressed at Centrica Storage's Easington site and stored under the southern North Sea using offshore infrastructure shared with the Teesside industrial cluster. Other ZCH partners will connect their infrastructure, currently in development, to the pipelines. Among them are bioenergy with CCS - BECCS at Drax Power Station near Selby, scaled up to become the world's first carbon negative power station by 2030, SSE Thermal's Keadby 3, near Scunthorpe, the UK's first gas-fired power station with CCS by the mid-2020s, at Uniper's Killingholme site in Immingham, clean hydrogen production¹³.

HyNet cluster project located in northwestern UK is based on the production of hydrogen from natural gas. It includes the development of a new hydrogen pipeline and the creation of the UK's first carbon capture, and storage infrastructure. HyNet saves over one Mt of CO₂ emissions every year in 2023-2026. In the second stage in 2027-2035 the project will increase potential savings for over 25 Mt CO₂ annually. In the last stage in 2035-2050 about 100 Mt CO₂ could be captured and stored. CO₂ will be stored in depleted gas reservoirs under the seabed of Liverpool Bay. Existing onshore and offshore pipelines will be reused for transporting CO₂. Current offshore platforms will be reused to facilitate CO₂ storage¹⁴. CO₂ will be transported by ships, 33 km offshore pipelines and 48 km onshore pipelines.

A Map of two UK CCUS scenarios are shown in Figure 7-1.

Porthos is a project in the Netherlands by the Port of Rotterdam authority, Gasunie and EBN to collect CO₂ from industry in the Rotterdam port area and transport it to storage locations offshore Rotterdam¹⁵. Porthos will act as an open-access utility for industries that have no viable decarbonization alternatives, such as refineries and the chemical sector. Four companies in the port area – Air Liquide, Air Products, ExxonMobil and Shell – will capture 2.5 million tonnes per year of carbon dioxide. Final Investment Decision in the project was taken in 2023 and the project is currently in construction phase. A notable aspect of the project is that it is a collaboration between state-owned entities.

¹³ <https://www.zerocarbonhumber.co.uk/>

¹⁴ <https://hynet.co.uk/>.

¹⁵ [Project - Porthos](#)

Figure 7-1 Map of two CCUS scenarios for three cluster projects in UK (Habicht, 2021).

8 Discussion

In this report we have discussed different challenges related to each part of the CCUS value chain. However, what is clear is that if one aims to develop a CCUS chain, all the present and future stakeholders along the value chain need to be informed and aligned. There are several main actors and driving forces that would be shaping CCUS value chains and these should be involved in the workflow. There is a strong interdependency of stakeholders with different interests, from industry with emitters, to transport and storage owners. To be able to reduce the risks, both economically and in terms of time spent, a strong consortium with all the stakeholders should be in place.

Reducing the uncertainty, both in storage capacity, storage injectivity and longevity of a storage site, is important. One major bottle neck at present, is the lack of open geological datasets, both 2D and 3D seismic dataset, and/or data from wells. We do not think it is a coincidence that the countries with the easiest access to data such as Norway, Denmark, UK and the Netherlands are in the forefront of underground CO₂ storage. In Denmark, most of the geology surveys have been carried out by Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) over the last decades. The overview of storage sites, transport, economical calculations are made available by the Danish Energy Agency and Energinet¹⁶. The state funding is based on injected CO₂. Thus, having a very transparent and politic process, Denmark has moved rapidly since 2020, when CO₂ storage offshore was allowed.

¹⁶ [Technology data for carbon capture transport and storage.pdf \(ens.dk\)](#)

Since it takes some years to mature a CO₂ storage site, also to mature and develop a CCUS value chain, it is important to build trust and transparency between the partners.

For CO₂ emitters, a hub structure is attractive (Wang 2024), to reduce the risk for each industry actor. A hub structure also reduces the risk that transport, and storage infrastructure will be underutilized. A hub with more emitters will be less dependent on the emissions of a single industrial site for maintaining a high degree of utilisation.

As a result of the development of common infrastructures for transporting and storing emissions from different industries, there is likely to be a need for common specifications for fluid composition and pressure/ temperature conditions (e.g. see Neerup et al. 2022). A better understanding of the reasons behind the limitations of the impurities given for the transport and storage infrastructure will make it easier to find solutions that is optimal in a whole chain perspective, and not only for parts of the chain. There is an ongoing debate if a common specification should be given to make it easier to transport CO₂ from different sources to several logistic network, or if each network should find its own specification based on the need for limitations related to their material choice, storage possibilities etc. The cost for extra purification is often high, and trying to find the lowest possible purification steps needed is crucial to reduce the cost.

In the screening, the total emissions amount of the clusters and the storage capacities are considered. However, it is recognised that actual total CO₂ emission volumes should be treated with caution. On one side, the total amount of the clusters' emission does not exactly represent the amount of captured CO₂, but rather a maximum, as not 100% of the emissions would necessarily be captured. For some industries transitioning to renewables or biogenic feed stocks may be more attractive and easier to implement.

8.1 CCS and CCU's role in the transition to zero-emissions

CCS and CCU represent some of the technology options we must have to move towards a zero-emission society. Renewable energy is obviously another form of technological contributor to this transition. Then there are technologies related to the use of hydrogen. There are also technologies for indirect or direct removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere (BECCS and DAC).

To move towards a zero-emission society in a fast and cost-efficient manner it will be important to have policymaking well-grounded in technical understanding of the potential of the different technologies.

In developing CCS value chains, one must consider where CCS is the most efficient approach to reducing emissions. It will therefore often be necessary to study CCS and CCU in the context of other options to mitigate CO₂ emissions.

For CCU it is important to be aware that it cannot contribute to reducing CO₂ emissions in the same way as CCS. There is no form of CO₂ utilisation that offers a combination of large-scale use of CO₂ with permanence of storage/binding (we are excluding Enhanced Oil Recovery from our definition of CCU in this case). CCU should rather be thought of as a circular way of using carbon.

9 Conclusions and recommendations for future CCUS cluster developments

The high level CCUS value chain screening can be summarised in with mapping of emitters, transport infrastructure and storage sites, and utilization as a theme closely connected to capture screening.

High-level CCUS value chain screening is the first step, evaluating the main tasks and research tasks that needs to be addressed. The screening should be a tool to gather interesting stakeholders for further work and future in-depth analysis. Thereafter, more input data, further analysis and modelling are needed to mature and qualify a CCUS value chain.

From the technical screening work performed, the main recommendations we can draw from for further development of CCUS value chains are:

- Include and anchor with all entities; also include research institutes and academia, in addition to government and NGOs in the process.
- Have all key stakeholders involved – actors from the whole CCUS chain.
- Design the value chain from an industrial and regional reality in order to provide a solution to an identified need.
- Improve geological knowledge to decrease uncertainties related to storage capacity and leakage risks.
- Improve access to data: Aim for open data and sharing of data. This is especially important for dataset linked to storage sites, to mature the site and level the Storage Readiness Level.
- Consider emitters from hard-to-abate industries (cement, etc.) as potential anchors for the clusters

We also recognise that non-technical aspect, such as legal regulations, social acceptance and economic factors, as covered in WP2 in CCUS ZEN are important factors also for the technical mapping.

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